

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

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Type

R Document, report

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.

OTHER

Dissemination Level

PU Public

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1st value chain event

The first EU value chain event of MAGIC project, organised in collaboration of PANACEA project, was focused on **oilseed crops** and took place at the premises of Imperial College London (UK) on 27/03/2018 and it was well attended by 46 participants from across the Europe. The agenda of the value-chain event is presented in the figure below.

Value Chain Event on Oilseed Crops

Imperial College London, 27/3/19
Skempton building (Lecture Theatre 201, Level 2)

8:30 - 9:00	Registration	
9:00 - 9:20	Welcome and set the scene of the today workshop	Calliope PANOUTSOU (ICP) & Efthymia ALEXOPOULOU (CRES)
9:20 – 10:50	Session 1: Chaired by Melvyn Askew (CENSUS BIO) & Spyros Kyritsis (AUA)	Efthymia ALEXOPOULOU (CRES)
	Promising oilseed crops for Europe: which ones can be grown on marginal lands?	
	Chemical industry needs from oilseed crops	Jean-Luc Dubois (ARKEMA)
	Camelina & crambe Oil crops as Sources for Medium-chain Oils for Specialty oleochemicals	Rolf Blaauw (WR)
	Sustainable camelina value chain in Spain	Yuri Herreras Yambanis (Camelina Company)
10:50-11:20	<i>Tea/ Coffee break</i>	
11:20-12:50	Session 2: Chaired by Spyros Kyritsis (AUA) & Melvyn Askew (CENSUS BIO)	
	Saving the rainforest? Environmental impacts of camelina and crambe	Nils Rettenmaier (ifeu)
	FIRST2RUN project	Cecilia Giardi (NOVAMONT)
	Developing harvesting systems for oil crops: the case of cardoon	Luigi Pari (CREA)
	BIO4A project	David Chiaramonti (RE-CORD)
12:50-13:40	<i>Lunch break</i>	
13:40-15:10	Session 3: Chaired by Melvyn Askew (CENSUS BIO) & Spyros Kyritsis (AUA)	
	The present status and challenges for cultivation of castor in Brazil	Liv Severino (EMPRAPA)
	Castor field trials in Italy on marginal lands	Luciano Cosentino (UNICT)
	Research on castor	Yuval Peles, KAIIMA
	Industrial hemp as oilseed crop	Niels de Beus (NOVA)
15:10-15:30	<i>Tea/coffee break</i>	
15:30-17:00	Session 4: working on three teams; cultivation, logistics, end-products	
17:00-17:30	Presentation of the findings of the discussions and wrap up	

The event is being supported by COSMOS project

The workshop was organised in four sessions; three had been dedicated on presentations of projects/products/activities on oilseeds, while in the last session the participants had been split in three teams and discussed: the agronomy of oilseeds, the logistics and the products. Below presented few photos from the oilseeds event.

The whole workshop concentrated on the following oilseed crops: camelina, crambe, castor, safflower, industrial hemp, cardoon and lupin for two reasons:

- ▶ considered as ready for practice (PANACEA project, www.panacea-h2020.eu) and
- ▶ being able to grown successfully on marginal lands facing natural constraints (MAGIC project, www.magic-h2020.eu)

On-going successful projects on oilseeds crops were presented as possibilities to increase the farmers' income though the access to new markets (high value biobased materials, biofuels, and bioenergy). Apart from MAGIC, cardoon had been established on marginal lands in Sardinia by NOVAMONT to produce valuable chemicals for the possible manufacture of a range of products including cosmetics and bioplastics. The goal of FIRST2RUN was harness the potential of local areas and builds a sustainable, profitable and job-creating value chain.

The value-chains of camelina and crambre were presented by COSMOS project (<http://cosmos-h2020.eu>) with sound field trials in Italy, Greece, Poland and the Netherlands with seed yields for both crops between 1.5 and 2.5 t seeds/ha and oil content around 40%. Camelina seems quite interesting oilseed crop (1-3 t/ha) that can be grown throughout Europe having an increasing industry demand and ability to be grown on marginal lands with seed yields (at least 1 tn/ha), having a short growing cycle allowing the double cropping in the existing agricultural systems and as feedstock for advanced aviantion biofuels (BIO2A project, www.bio4a.eu).

It should be pointed out that the area of industrial hemp has been tripled from 2014 to 2018 and this increased was the result of the increasing demand for hemp seeds and CBD.

At the same time an increased production area was recorded in the Mediterranean countries. Lupin is a challenging oil and carbohydrate crop able to be grown on marginal lands as feedstock for cosmetics and other value added bioproducts (LIBBIO project, www.libbio.net).

The presentations of the event have been uploaded at: <http://magic-h2020.eu/scientific-publications/>, under the 1st Value Chain Event on Oilseed Crops, Imperial College London 27/03/19 (see below)

In this section, you will find the presentations of the 1st Value Chain Event of the MAGIC project in collaboration with PANACEA and COSMOS.

1. [Promising oilseed crops for Europe which could be grown on marginal lands](#) (by Efi Alexopoulpou, CRES)
2. [Bioeconomy as Territorial Regeneration](#) (Cecilia Gardi, NOVAMONT)
3. [Chemical Industry Needs from Oilseed Crops](#) (by Jean-Luc Dubois, ARKEMA)
4. [The present status and challenges for cultivation of castor in Brazil](#) (by Liv Severino, EMPRAPA)
5. [Developing harvesting systems for oil crops the case of cardoon](#) (by Luigi Pari, CREA)
6. [Saving the rainforest Environmental impacts of camellia and crambe](#) (by Nils Rettenmaier, IFEU)
7. [Industrial hemp as oilseed crop](#) (Niels de Beus, nova-Institut)
8. [LINNIO Lupin Beauty from marginal soils](#) (by Rob Van Haren, Haze University of Applied Science & Irmhard Szarman (ZoiY natural cosmetics))
9. [Sustainable camelina value chain in Spain](#) (by Yuri Herreras Yambanis, Camelina Company)
10. [What is needed for the next phase in Castors evolution?](#) (by Yuval Peles)